

Phenomenological Aerodynamic Analysis of an Ejector Exposed to Large Inlet Pulsations

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To enable the coupling of the unsteady, high-enthalpy flow exiting a Rotating Detonation Combustor (RDC) with a subsonic turbine, an ejector may be installed between combustor and turbine. In the present work, a conventional ejector is investigated numerically using a Large-Eddy Simulation. Firstly, a stationary operating point is analyzed where sufficient agreement could be obtained with experimental data. Secondly, a new operating point is proposed where a sinusoidal acoustic pulsation is imposed at the primary ejector inlet. The pulsation generates a periodic fluctuation between sub- and supersonic velocity regimes at the primary nozzle exit, which is representative of local RDC exhaust velocities. In this first step, the exhaust gas temperature, flow angle, and gas composition are not considered. At this operating condition, a secondary normal shock appears periodically at the end of the constant-area mixing chamber and retracts upstream as a pressure wave. The shear layer, the boundary layer, the secondary shock and the diffuser-induced separation are identified as kinetic energy loss sources within the ejector. The amplitude of total pressure fluctuations is reduced by 85% throughout the device, whereas the frequency is retained. The dampening characteristics are considered favorable for gas turbine integration.

Nomenclature

Symbols

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A	=	Velocity pulsation amplitude [m s^{-1}]
B	=	Integration constant [-]
c	=	Sound speed [m s^{-1}]
C_a	=	Cook and Cabot model constant [-]
C_p	=	Heat capacity at constant pressure [$\text{J kg}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$]
C_S	=	Smagorinsky model constant [-]
C_v	=	Heat capacity at constant volume [$\text{J kg}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$]
d	=	Diameter [m]
d_{mc}	=	Mixing chamber diameter [m]
d_o	=	Outlet section diameter [m]
D	=	Min-Max factor [-]
e_s	=	Sensible energy [J kg^{-1}]
E	=	Energy [J kg^{-1}]
f	=	Frequency [Hz]
F	=	Cut-off filter function [-]
\mathcal{F}_C	=	Convective fluxes [-]
\mathcal{F}_V	=	Viscous fluxes [-]
G_P	=	Static pressure relative error [-]
G_Π	=	Kinetic energy dissipation relative error [-]
J	=	Mass flux [$\text{kg s}^{-1} \text{m}^{-2}$]
K_u	=	Velocity ratio [-]
K_ρ	=	Density ratio [-]
L	=	Integral length scale [m s^{-1}]
\dot{m}	=	Mass flow rate [kg s^{-1}]
M	=	Mach number [-]
M_c	=	Convective Mach number [-]
P	=	Pressure [bar]
Pr	=	Prandtl number [-]
q	=	Heat flux vector [W m^{-2}]
R	=	Specific gas constant [$\text{J kg}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$]
Re	=	Reynolds number [-]
S	=	Strain rate tensor [s^{-1}]

\dot{S}_{gen}	=	Irreversible entropy generation rate [$\text{W m}^{-3} \text{K}^{-1}$]
t	=	Time [s]
t_c	=	Convective time [s]
T	=	Temperature [K]
u	=	Axial velocity [m s^{-1}]
u_τ	=	Friction velocity [m s^{-1}]
U	=	Velocity field [m s^{-1}]
v_{RMS}	=	RMS of transverse velocity [m s^{-1}]
w	=	Vector of conservative variables [-]
x, y, z	=	Spatial coordinate [m]
δ_w	=	Vorticity thickness [m]
δ_{ij}	=	Kronecker delta [-]
Δ	=	Grid size [m]
Δ_x	=	Cook and Cabot characteristic length [m]
η_k	=	Kolmogorov length scale [m]
κ	=	Von-Karman constant [-]
λ	=	Thermal conductivity [$\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$]
μ	=	Dynamic viscosity [$\text{kg m}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$]
μ_a	=	Artificial dynamic viscosity [$\text{kg m}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$]
ν	=	Kinematic viscosity [$\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$]
ξ	=	Dampening factor [-]
Π_{KE}	=	Loss in kinetic energy [W m^{-3}]
Π_{TE}	=	Loss in thermal energy [W m^{-3}]
ρ	=	Density [kg m^{-3}]
τ	=	Viscous stress tensor [N m^{-2}]
ω	=	Entrainment ratio [-]

Subscripts

1	=	Primary inlet
2	=	Secondary inlet
3	=	Diffuser exit
4	=	Discharge/Outlet

i, j, k = Spatial coordinate indices
 $ne1$ = Primary nozzle exit
 $ne2$ = Secondary nozzle exit
 s = Static
 t = Total
 w = Wall

Superscripts

A = Area-averaged
 Exp = Experimental
 LES = Large-Eddy Simulation
 \dot{m} = Mass-flow averaged
 SGS = Subgrid-Scale

I. Introduction

Due to their potential efficiency improvement in contrast to constant-pressure combustion systems, Pressure Gain Combustion (PGC) technologies have gained significant interest in recent decades. Rotating Detonation Combustors (RDCs) are a notable example, featuring one or multiple detonation waves continuously circulating around a typically annular, hollow, or disk-shaped combustion chamber. Apart from their capacity to eliminate CO₂ emissions when operated with hydrogen fuel, their sustained operation in the 1 - 100 kHz range [1] makes RDCs an appealing option for integration into turbomachinery applications [2, 3].

However, the transonic, high-enthalpy exhaust gas stemming from the unsteady combustion in the RDC is an inherent challenge associated with turbomachinery integration due to its possibly adverse affects on turbine performance. Klopsch et al. [4] conducted a numerical investigation of an annular RDC using a 2D Euler solver. Their findings revealed that an increasing mass flux leads to a higher outlet Mach number. At the lowest mass flux tested, the outlet remained entirely subsonic, with Mach number fluctuations ranging from 0.25 to 0.9. In contrast, for the highest mass flux employed, the outlet Mach number was consistently at least sonic. Tobias et al. [5] carried out an experimental study on an annular RDC, measuring an axial velocity fluctuation between 500 and 1500 m s⁻¹, along with an azimuthal velocity fluctuation ranging from -500 to 300 m s⁻¹. The study also concluded that both axial and azimuthal velocity oscillations decrease with a reduction in mass flow rate. Naples et al. [6] recorded a static pressure oscillation in the RDC outlet plane varying between approximately 0.8 and 1.8 bar, at a frequency of about 2.9 kHz.

To alleviate adverse effects linked to the integration of an RDC with a turbine, one possible strategy involves propelling the exhaust gas from the RDC into a strictly supersonic regime. The supersonic flow is then admitted into either a supersonic turbine [7] or a novel bladeless turbine [8]. Conversely, for driving a subsonic turbine, various authors have suggested the use of an ejector or mixer positioned between the RDC chamber and the turbine [2, 3, 6]. Unrelated to RDC applications, conventional ejectors have been tested extensively in previous studies, both experimentally and numerically [9]. In an ejector, a primary flow is accelerated in a converging-diverging nozzle, where a leading normal shock wave is located at the nozzle exit at typical operating points. The primary jet then expands in a mixing chamber, forming a Mach stem downstream of the nozzle exit. In turn, this induces a low-pressure region that entrains a secondary flow. Both flows then undergo a mixing process in the mixing chamber, which is either designed for constant-pressure mixing (at variable cross-sectional area), or constant-area mixing (at variable pressures) [9]. Throughout this process, mass (in the case of different compositions), momentum and energy are transferred from the primary to the secondary flow [10]. Mixing of both flows in a constant-area mixing chamber can be categorized into several phases as suggested by Croquer et al. [11]: Close to the primary nozzle exit, the shear layer between both flows is laminar. Further downstream, it transitions to turbulence and eventually becomes fully turbulent. Depending on the operating point, at some axial distance from the nozzle exit, the influence of the boundary layer becomes significant, i.e. the maximum transverse velocity gradient is located in the boundary layer (and not in the shear layer any longer). There are generally 3 flow regimes in an ejector, which are governed by the entrainment ratio $\omega = \dot{m}_2/\dot{m}_1$ and the discharge pressure P_{s4} [9, 12]: (1) The critical or on-design operating regimes which are characterized by ω being constant, thus both primary and secondary flows being choked, and the discharge pressure P_{s4} being below its critical value; (2) the subcritical or off-design operating regime which are identified by ω decreasing with increasing P_{s4} , the secondary flow being unchoked, but with P_{s4} still below its critical value; and (3) the backflow or malfunctioning regimes where P_{s4} is above its critical value, leading to backflow in the secondary flow channel. Typical values of the entrainment ratio in conventional ejectors are $\omega < 1.2 - 1.3$ [9].

The application of the working principle of an ejector to RDC - turbine coupling introduces several design objectives that are not addressed in conventional ejector research. In order to obtain subsonic turbine inlet conditions, (statistically steady flow with $M \approx 0.15$ [13]) the ejector is required to dampen the fluctuations and to decelerate the combustor exhaust gas. To retain the pressure gain inherent to RDCs, minimizing losses throughout this process is of importance [14]. The ratio between secondary inlet pressure and discharge pressure, which is a performance parameter of classical ejectors, is consequently of less significance when the ejector is integrated in an RDC - turbine application. The installation of an ejector for RDC - subsonic turbine coupling was proposed in the experimental work by Naples et al. [6]. Static pressure fluctuations stemming from the RDC exhaust could be decreased by 60-70%. The dampening of pressure oscillations was ascribed to both pressure wave expansion and energy transfer to the secondary flow within the ejector. The ratio of bypass to RDC mass flow rate tested was up to 4.0, which is significantly elevated compared to the

entrainment ratio in classical ejectors. Paxson and Naples [15] combined numerical predictions of an RDC with an analytical mixing calculation in a downstream ejector. The results were then applied to a numerical T63 helicopter engine cycle setup (replacing the classical constant-pressure combustion chamber), where a turbine adiabatic efficiency of 0.83 could be obtained. At this operating point, the ratio of bypass to RDC mass flow rate was roughly 3.0. In a subsequent experimental study [3], a conventional constant-pressure combustor was correlated to the RDC-ejector configuration, both separately integrated in a T63 helicopter engine. The integration of the RDC and ejector in this engine resulted in a turbine efficiency comparable to that of an integrated classical constant-pressure combustor, both at around 0.75. The experimental setup involved testing four operating points with dilution to RDC mass flow ratios ranging from 2.7 to 5.3. Apart from the presented studies, the research published in the field of RDC - turbine coupling with an ejector, to the author's knowledge, is relatively limited, especially with regard to higher-fidelity computations, and there is a need to further address this crucial problem for gas turbine integration of RDCs.

The temporally and spatially oscillating nature of the RDC exhaust gas favors an unsteady numerical modeling approach such as Large-Eddy Simulation (LES), to adequately capture the relevant physics of an ejector or mixer downstream of an RDC. In the current study, a numerical investigation of an ejector exposed to pulsating flow is conducted, considering only the temporal unsteadiness as a first step. The work is two-fold; initially, an existing, conventional ejector configuration [12] at a standard stationary operating point is modeled and results are compared to available experimental data, in order to ensure an accurate prediction of complex flow phenomena. Subsequently, the operating point is completely changed and unsteady inflow with time-magnitude oscillations representative of an RDC exhaust is imposed, aiming at an examination of the unsteady mixing physics within the ejector from an aerodynamic perspective. This study represents a necessary first step in the attempt to link well-understood conventional ejectors and an ejector integrated with an RDC. As a consequence, temperature, flow angle, and species fluctuations typical of an RDC exhaust are not considered.

II. Configuration and Numerical Approach

The numerical analysis is conducted using the compressible, multi-species code AVBP [16] that solves the filtered Navier-Stokes equations for Large-Eddy Simulation (LES) on unstructured grids with explicit time integration. It has been validated for a number of compressible flow configurations and is thus deemed suitable for this study [11, 17].

A. Governing Equations

The governing equations for Large-Eddy Simulation (LES) are based on a mass-weighted Favre filtering operation of the form $\bar{\rho}\tilde{\psi}(\mathbf{x}) = \overline{\rho\psi}(\mathbf{x}) = \int \rho\psi(\mathbf{x}')F(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}')d\mathbf{x}'$, where $\bar{\rho}$ and $\tilde{\psi}$ are the filtered density (denoted by the $\bar{\star}$ symbol) and a mass-weighted filtered quantity of interest (denoted by the $\tilde{\star}$ -symbol), respectively, F is a cut-off filter function

and \mathbf{x} is the spatial coordinate vector. Applying the filtering on the instantaneous Navier-Stokes equations leads to the following set of equations for a non-reacting, single species compressible flow [18, 19]:

$$\frac{\partial \bar{\rho}}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial (\bar{\rho} \tilde{U}_i)}{\partial x_i} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial (\bar{\rho} \tilde{U}_i)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial (\bar{\rho} \tilde{U}_i \tilde{U}_j)}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial \bar{P}}{\partial x_j} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} (\tilde{\tau}_{ij} - \tau_{ij}^{SGS}) \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial (\bar{\rho} \tilde{E}_t)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial (\bar{\rho} \tilde{U}_i \tilde{E}_t)}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial (\bar{P} \tilde{U}_i)}{\partial x_i} = -\frac{\partial \tilde{q}_i}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial (\tilde{\tau}_{ij} \tilde{U}_i)}{\partial x_j} - \frac{\partial q_i^{SGS}}{\partial x_i} - \frac{\partial (\tau_{ij}^{SGS} \tilde{U}_i)}{\partial x_j} \quad (3)$$

Here, \tilde{U}_i is the i -th component of the filtered velocity field, \bar{P} is the filtered pressure, and \tilde{E}_t is the filtered total energy, $\tilde{E}_t = \tilde{e}_s + (\tilde{U}_i \tilde{U}_i)/2$ (\tilde{e}_s is the filtered sensible energy). The terms q_i and τ_{ij} refer to the heat flux vector and viscous stress tensor, respectively, which consist of a filtered (\tilde{q}_i , $\tilde{\tau}_{ij}$) and subgrid-scale (SGS) (q_i^{SGS} , τ_{ij}^{SGS}) contribution. The filtered viscous stress tensor is based on a Newtonian fluid assumption and calculated as:

$$\tilde{\tau}_{ij} = 2\mu \tilde{S}_{ij} - \frac{2}{3}\mu \frac{\partial \tilde{U}_k}{\partial x_k} \delta_{ij} \quad (4)$$

In Eq. 4, μ is the dynamic, laminar viscosity of the fluid, which is obtained as a function of temperature using Sutherland's law for air with appropriate coefficients [20]. For air at 295 K, $\mu = 1.82 \times 10^{-5} \text{ kg m}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The parameter δ_{ij} refers to the Kronecker symbol ($\delta_{ij} = 1$ if $i = j$, $\delta_{ij} = 0$ otherwise) and \tilde{S}_{ij} is the filtered strain rate tensor given by:

$$\tilde{S}_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial \tilde{U}_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial \tilde{U}_j}{\partial x_i} \right) \quad (5)$$

The filtered heat flux vector is given as a Fourier term:

$$\tilde{q}_i = -\lambda \frac{\partial \tilde{T}}{\partial x_i} \quad (6)$$

where the parameter \tilde{T} is the filtered temperature and λ is the laminar thermal conductivity, $\lambda = \mu C_p / Pr$. The molecular Prandtl number Pr is set to 0.69, a standard value for air [20], and the heat capacity at constant pressure C_p is derived as a function of temperature using the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) JANAF database [21]. C_p is constant for windows of 100 K in the range between 0 and 5000 K; the value for a given temperature is then extracted using linear interpolation [22]. For air at 295 K, $C_p = 1006 \text{ J kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$. The system of equations, Eqs. 1 to 3, is closed by assuming a thermally and calorically perfect gas:

$$\bar{P} = \bar{\rho} R \tilde{T} \quad , \quad \tilde{e}_s = C_v \tilde{T} \quad (7)$$

Here, C_v is the heat capacity at constant volume. The value of C_v , as for C_p , is derived from the JANAF database [21] and linearly interpolated for a given temperature. At 295 K, $C_v = 717.3 \text{ J kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$; R is the specific gas constant. This concludes the description of the filtered quantities, i.e. the quantities predicted by the numerical solver. The terms previously introduced, q_i^{SGS} and τ_{ij}^{SGS} , account for the subgrid-scale contributions and are modeled, as is required in a LES context. In the current work, the classical Smagorinsky model [23] is employed to account for subgrid-scale viscous stress contributions, which has been used in other studies of supersonic shear layers [24]. Utilizing the Boussinesq assumption, the subgrid-scale viscous stress tensor is of the general form:

$$\tau_{ij}^{SGS} - \frac{1}{3} \tau_{kk}^{SGS} \delta_{ij} = -2\mu^{SGS} \left(\tilde{S}_{ij} - \frac{1}{3} \frac{\partial \tilde{U}_k}{\partial x_k} \delta_{ij} \right) = -2\bar{\rho} (C_S \Delta)^2 (2\tilde{S}_{ij} \tilde{S}_{ij})^{1/2} \left(\tilde{S}_{ij} - \frac{1}{3} \frac{\partial \tilde{U}_k}{\partial x_k} \delta_{ij} \right) \quad (8)$$

where μ^{SGS} is the subgrid-scale dynamic viscosity, $C_S = 0.18$ is a model constant, and Δ is the grid size. The term τ_{kk}^{SGS} in Eq. 8 is neglected in AVBP and $\partial \tilde{U}_k / \partial x_k \approx 0$ is assumed. For the respective heat flux term, a gradient assumption is employed:

$$q_i^{SGS} = \lambda^{SGS} \frac{\partial \tilde{T}}{\partial x_i} \quad (9)$$

The subgrid-scale thermal conductivity λ^{SGS} is derived analogously to the laminar thermal conductivity, using the subgrid-scale viscosity and a subgrid-scale Prandtl number, $\lambda^{SGS} = \mu^{SGS} C_p / Pr^{SGS}$, where $Pr^{SGS} = 0.6$.

B. Numerical Methodology

The Navier-Stokes equations in vector form, where the filtering nomenclature from the previous section has been omitted, read [16]:

$$\frac{\partial w}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \mathcal{F} = 0 \quad (10)$$

In Eq. 10, w is the vector of conservative variables (ρ , ρU_i and ρE_t) and \mathcal{F} is a vector of convective and viscous fluxes, $\mathcal{F} = \mathcal{F}_C(w) + \mathcal{F}_V(w, \nabla w)$. The convective flux term \mathcal{F}_C is discretized using a Taylor-Galerkin finite element scheme that has 3rd order space and 4th order time accuracy [25, 26]. The scheme is implemented in AVBP using a cell-vertex formulation, which is detailed by Schönfeld and Rudgyard [16]. This discretization is implicit for the unknown variables, which requires a matrix inversion. This inversion is generally costly, hence, a Jacobi approximation of the inversion operation is employed. The viscous fluxes \mathcal{F}_V are implemented using a finite element scheme in a vertex-centered formulation.

A common issue with centered schemes is the introduction of dispersive errors. The viscous operator is generally insufficient to dissipate them at high Reynolds numbers typical for LES. An option to overcome this issue is the use of artificial scalar diffusion. In the present work, a Colin sensor is applied that introduces second-order and fourth-order artificial diffusion [27]. The sensor has been developed for unsteady, turbulent computations based on the Jameson sensor [28]. The latter is linearly dependent on the second derivative of a quantity of interest, whereas the Colin sensor uses a non-linear hyperbolic tangent relation to increase its sharpness. This ensures very low artificial diffusion in regions with sufficient resolution, and maximum artificial diffusion in regions with non-linearities. The second-order sensor acts on all conservative flow variables ρ , ρU_i and ρE_t to smoothen large gradients, whereas the fourth-order sensor only acts on ρ and ρE_t to dampen node-to-node oscillations. The generated artificial diffusion terms are added to the node residuals in the cell-vertex formulation. The detailed implementation in AVBP is reported elsewhere [27].

In addition, the presence of discontinuities in the fluid domain, which are expected in an ejector simulation, could lead to local over- or undershoots of flow variables, even with reasonable gradient smoothing due to added artificial diffusion. With a typical shock wave thickness of the order of 10^{-7} m, fully resolving such flow features is impractical. Thus, adding a shock handling model to the computation is a viable option. In the current work, the model proposed by Cook and Cabot [29] is employed, which adds an additional compression viscosity to the diagonal entries of the laminar viscous stress tensor (Eq. 4). The added artificial viscosity is of the form:

$$\mu_a = C_a \rho (\Delta_x)^4 |\widehat{\nabla^2 S_{ij} S_{ij}}| \quad (11)$$

The parameter $C_a = 5$ is a constant and Δ_x is a characteristic length. A Gaussian filter is applied to the shear stress term, which is approximated by a cell average in AVBP. Due to the dependence on $\nabla \cdot U_i$ (see the second term of Eq. 4), the additional term has no impact in regions where $\nabla \cdot U_i \approx 0$. Further details of the model are given in appropriate literature[29].

The presented LES is wall-modeled to keep the computational efforts reasonable, and all walls are adiabatic. Fully resolving the near-wall region would increase grid count significantly, scaling with $Re^{13/7}$ [30]. The employed model is a logarithmic Law-of-the-Wall [31]:

$$\frac{u}{u_\tau} = \kappa^{-1} \ln \left(B \frac{y u_\tau}{\nu} \right) \quad (12)$$

where $\kappa = 0.41$ is the von Karman constant, $B = 9.2$ is an integration constant, u is the axial velocity, u_τ is the friction velocity, y is the first grid point distance from the wall and ν is the kinematic viscosity. Equation 12 is solved iteratively for the friction velocity u_τ , which is then used to compute the wall shear stress, $\tau_w = \rho u_\tau^2$. Since the classical SGS model of Smagorinsky introduced in Eq. 8 reverts in the near-wall region to a mixing-length type model, it is

well compatible with the logarithmic Law-of-the-Wall, where the majority of turbulence in the near-wall region is not resolved [31].

C. Ejector Setup, Boundary Conditions and Initialization

The studied configuration in this work is the experimentally tested ejector of Kracik and Dvorak [12], which is shown schematically in Fig. 1 and has been numerically investigated in a previous study [32]. In the ejector, the primary flow (index 1) accelerates in a converging-diverging nozzle, mixes with the entrained secondary flow (index 2) in a constant-area mixing chamber, and finally enters a diffuser and constant-area outlet section (index 4). The reader is referred to the work of Kracik and Dvorak [12] for further specifics.

Fig. 1 Schematic and main geometric parameters of the ejector configuration. Reprinted from Uhl et al. [32].

Inlet and outlet boundaries are represented by Navier-Stokes Characteristic Boundary Conditions (NSCBC). At the primary inlet, axial velocity u_1 and static temperature T_{s1} are enforced [33]. The secondary inlet boundary is characterized by total pressure P_{t2} and total temperature T_{t2} [34], whereas at the outlet, static pressure P_{s4} is imposed [35]. The sole boundary quantities published for the primary ejector inlet are P_{t1} and T_{t1} [12], hence, for the initialization, done on a coarse computational grid, P_{t1} and T_{t1} are enforced for the primary inlet (instead of u_1 and T_{s1}). After obtaining the initial flow field, the solution is interpolated on a fine grid (see section II.D). The primary inlet axial velocity u_1 and static temperature T_{s1} are extracted from the initialization and subsequently imposed for the full computation. This procedure of switching the primary inlet boundary condition is done in preparation for the unsteady inlet case that is detailed in the following paragraphs. The conditions correspond to a stationary operating point, termed OP1-Exp, that was investigated experimentally by Kracik and Dvorak [12].

Additionally, in order to generate a primary flow representative of an RDC exhaust, a completely new operating point, termed OP2-U, is proposed. This operating point is designed to ensure a continuous choking and unchoking of the flow at the primary nozzle throat when appropriate pulsations are imposed, in turn generating the typical transonic Mach number range of an RDC exhaust (see section I) at the primary nozzle exit. Hence, in this study, the primary nozzle exit is the section of the ejector considered representative of the RDC exhaust.

An existing LES of an RDC chamber has been evaluated as a reference [36] to obtain appropriate pulsations for this new operating point OP2-U. Instantaneous results in the mean diameter of the RDC outlet section indicated that for the

investigated engine and operating point, the axial velocity component is dominating in the velocity magnitude with respect to radial and tangential components. The relative error in velocity magnitude over a single RDC period when ignoring tangential and radial components entirely is less than 5% [36]. Thus, it is a reasonable first assumption to neglect the non-axial velocity components at the RDC outlet and to only retain a pulsation of the axial velocity, which is done in the present work. The effect of mean temperature and fluctuations, as well as species and flow angle variations are not accounted for. Thus, a sinusoidal pulsation of the form $u_1 = \bar{u}_1 + A_1 \sin(2\pi f_1 t)$ (where \bar{u}_1 refers to the mean axial velocity at the primary flow inlet; A_1 and f_1 specify the primary flow inlet velocity fluctuation amplitude and frequency, respectively) is generated at the primary inlet using the NSCBC formalism from Daviller et al. [37], i.e. by imposing an acoustic perturbation on the mean flow (hence, pressure is pulsated accordingly). The amplitude A_1 was fixed at 100 m s^{-1} to ensure the previously mentioned periodic choking and unchoking of the primary nozzle throat. The signal has a frequency f_1 of 1 kHz, which is on the lower end of the frequency spectrum of typical RDC exhaust signals. The typical RDC exhaust gas pressure characteristic, a steep increase due to shock wave passing followed by a relaxation, is not completely captured by this modeling. However, a sinusoidal signal to mimic RDC exhaust gas characteristics has been shown to be adequate in other studies [38]. To prevent backflow in the secondary channel when the primary nozzle exit velocity is low (i.e. approaching the ejector malfunctioning regime mentioned in section I), the secondary total pressure P_{t2} had to be set equal to the outlet static pressure P_{s4} for OP2-U. As for the experimental steady case OP1-Exp, the flow is initialized on a coarse mesh and subsequently interpolated on the actual finer grid used in this study (see section II.D). A characteristic boundary condition, where P_{t1} and T_{t1} are imposed, is again used at the primary inlet for the initialization. The boundary values imposed for both operating points OP1-Exp and OP2-U are summarized in Tab. 1.

Table 1 Boundary values imposed for the ejector computation with operating point OP1-Exp and OP2-U

	OP1-Exp		OP2-U	
	Initialization	Simulation	Initialization	Simulation
P_{t1}	296.82 kPa	-	210.0 kPa	-
T_{t1}	295 K	-	295 K	-
\bar{u}_1	-	23.64 m s^{-1}	-	23.07 m s^{-1}
T_{s1}	-	295 K	-	295 K
A_1	-	-	-	100 m s^{-1}
f_1	-	-	-	1 kHz
P_{t2}	97 kPa	97 kPa	117.37 kPa	117.37 kPa
T_{t2}	295 K	295 K	295 K	295 K
P_{s4}	117.37 kPa	117.37 kPa	117.37 kPa	117.37 kPa

D. Grid

The computational grid was obtained after a grid size analysis study, performed for OP1-Exp. Four fully tetrahedral grids were tested with a cell size of roughly 12, 25, 52 and 105 million, which led to a minimum cell volume between $1.2 \times 10^{-14} \text{ m}^3$ for the coarsest and $5.9 \times 10^{-16} \text{ m}^3$ for the finest mesh. Two quantities of interest were defined for the grid convergence study. Firstly, the relative error with respect to experimental data in time-averaged static pressure predictions along the constant-area mixing chamber wall ($0 < x/d_{mc} < 12$, where d_{mc} is the mixing chamber diameter, see Fig. 1), defined as $G_P = \left| (\bar{P}_{s,w}^{LES} - P_{s,w}^{Exp}) / P_{s,w}^{Exp} \right|$, was investigated. Secondly, the relative error in time-averaged kinetic energy dissipation Π_{KE} along the jet centerline with respect to the finest grid, defined as $G_\Pi = \left| (\Pi_{KE} - \Pi_{KE}^{105m}) / \Pi_{KE}^{105m} \right|$, was evaluated. G_Π was normalized using the relative error of the coarsest (12m) mesh (termed G_Π^{12m}). Both quantities are considered relevant for accurate predictions of internal flow phenomena in the ejector. Figure 2 shows G_P and G_Π/G_Π^{12m} for all evaluated grids.

(a) Relative error of static pressure at mixing chamber wall with respect to exp. data (reprinted from Uhl et al. [32]) (b) Normalized relative error of centerline kinetic energy dissipation with respect to finest grid

Fig. 2 Effect of grid resolution on computational predictions

The relative error in wall static pressure predictions with respect to experimental data is decreasing notably between the coarsest (12m) and the second-finest mesh (52m), both in terms of absolute values and standard deviation (Fig. 2a). For the finest mesh, the standard deviation is further decreased but no significant improvement is observed in the relative error. A decrease in relative error is evident for kinetic energy dissipation predictions on the jet centerline between the coarsest (12m) and second-coarsest (25m) grid (Fig. 2b). Further refinement continues to reduce the error but at much smaller increments. As a result of analyzing G_P and G_Π , the second-finest mesh (52m) with 51,857,827 tetrahedral cells and 9,111,851 million nodes is chosen for the current study. To further assess mesh quality, the criterion proposed by Bellan [19] for supersonic jets, $L/d_{ne1} \gg \Delta/d_{ne1} \gg \eta_K/d_{ne1}$, is evaluated at the nozzle exit of the ejector. This strategy has been used in other studies focusing on LES of supersonic ejectors [11]. The parameter d_{ne1} is the

primary jet nozzle exit diameter; whereas L , Δ and η_k specify the integral length scale, a characteristic cell size and the Kolmogorov length scale, respectively. For supersonic jets, $L/d_{ne1} \sim 0.1 - 0.5$ is a reasonable assumption [19], $\Delta/d_{ne1} = 0.006 - 0.022$ for the chosen grid sizes, and $\eta_k/d_{ne1} = (L/d_{ne1})^{0.25} Re_{ne1}^{-0.75} = 0.7 - 1.0 \times 10^{-4}$ [19], with a Reynolds number of the jet at the nozzle exit $Re_{ne1} = (\bar{u}_{ne1}d_{ne1})/\nu_{ne1} = 1.68 \times 10^5$ for OP1-Exp. The parameters Re_{ne1} , \bar{u}_{ne1} and ν_{ne1} refer to primary jet nozzle exit conditions (Reynolds number, time-averaged axial velocity and kinematic viscosity, respectively). The computational grid is presented in Fig. 3 with a zoomed view on the nozzle exit section.

Fig. 3 Fully tetrahedral, unstructured grid (top), with a zoomed view on the nozzle exit section (bottom). Reprinted from Uhl et al. [32].

E. Run Details

The steady simulation (OP1-Exp) was run for 2 convective times after transitory initialization, whereas the unsteady simulation (OP2-U) was run for 3 convective times (corresponds to 25 periods). The mean timestep size with the selected grid was 1.8×10^{-8} s, with a Courant-Friedrichs-Lewy (CFL) number set to 0.7. The computations were run using 14 AMD nodes, each with 256 GB RAM and 128 cores. The simulation of one convective time required about 28,700 CPU hours, with a wall clock time of roughly 16 hours.

III. Results and Discussion

A. Analysis of Existing Steady Operating Point OP1-Exp

1. Comparison to Experimental Data

This section discusses the comparison with experimental data for OP1-Exp, which is an operating point in the subcritical regime, i.e. the secondary flow is unchoked at the nozzle exit [12]. Figure 4 shows time-averaged wall static pressure, normalized with the secondary inlet total pressure P_{t2} , in comparison to the experimental and RANS results of Kracik and Dvorak [12]. The LES predictions of wall static pressure agree well with experimental data. At $x/d_{mc} = 4$, the supersonic jet starts interacting with the channel boundary layer, which leads to an increase in wall static pressure measurements. The effect is well captured by the LES, and this zone also corresponds to the highest fluctuations

in the domain. Between $6 < x/d_{mc} < 12$, static pressure is slightly overestimated in the computational predictions. Nevertheless, the average relative error with respect to experimental data could be reduced to 3.3% with the LES (compared to the RANS error of 4.7% [12]). The time-averaged LES entrainment ratio $\omega = \dot{m}_2/\dot{m}_1$ amounted to 0.964. Considering the experimental result of 0.918, this is a significant improvement in comparison to the RANS prediction of 1.061 [12]. The sufficient agreement of wall static pressure and entrainment ratio predictions with measurements confirms the suitability of the numerical setup for this configuration.

Fig. 4 Time-averaged LES wall static pressure, in comparison to RANS and experimental data [12] for OP1-Exp. Reprinted from Uhl et al. [32].

2. Flow Field Description

Figure 5 depicts an instantaneous snapshot of a Q-criterion isosurface, colored by vorticity, and drawn over the instantaneous density gradient magnitude field. Additionally, the figure includes the normalized root-mean-square (RMS) transverse velocity, v_{RMS}/\bar{u}_{ne1} across various axial planes. The velocity used for normalization \bar{u}_{ne1} is the time-averaged nozzle exit axial velocity. In proximity of the primary nozzle exit for $x/d_{mc} \leq 1$, the amplitude of transverse velocity fluctuations is small; thus, minimal mixing occurs between primary and secondary flow. The primary flow shock diamond structures form distinctly in this region (Fig. 5a). The symmetrical v_{RMS} profile in Fig. 5b shows that shear layer growth is nearly equal at the upper and lower interfaces between primary and secondary flow. For $x/d_{mc} = 2$ and $x/d_{mc} = 3$ (Figs. 5c and 5d), the amplitude of transverse velocity fluctuations augments. Although two distinctive peaks persist, the profile symmetry diminishes and turbulent structures appear. Within $1 < x/d_{mc} \leq 2$, the shock train encounters minimal perturbation, whereas for $2 < x/d_{mc} \leq 3$, it starts dissipating and mixing between both flows commences. At $x/d_{mc} = 4$ (Fig. 5e), the amplitude of transverse velocity fluctuations peaks, the primary and secondary flows become less distinguishable and the influence of the boundary layer is apparent for $|y/d_{mc}| \rightarrow 0.5$.

For $x/d_{mc} = 6$ and $x/d_{mc} = 8$ (Figs. 5f and 5g), the fluctuations diminish which indicates that the mixing process is terminating. Qualitatively, a mixed turbulent pipe flow is present in the domain at $x/d_{mc} = 8$, and only the relatively small-scale turbulent structures persist which dissipate further downstream.

Fig. 5 (a) Q-criterion colored by vorticity over the density gradient magnitude and, reprinted from Uhl et al. [32], (b)-(g) profiles of the RMS of the transverse velocity for OP1-Exp

3. Shear Layer Development and Comparison to Empirical Growth Value

In an attempt to characterize the accuracy of predicting internal physics of the ejector with the selected computational setup, shear layer development for OP1-Exp is analyzed. To do so, vorticity thickness δ_w is retained as a metric. The same parameter has been used in other high-fidelity computational studies of air-air ejectors [11] and more generally, in studies of mixing layers [39], and reads:

$$\delta_w = \frac{\bar{u}_{ne1} - \bar{u}_{ne2}}{\max\left(\left|\frac{\partial \bar{U}}{\partial y}\right|\right)} \quad (13)$$

In Eq. 13, \bar{u}_{ne1} and \bar{u}_{ne2} are the time-averaged nozzle exit axial velocities for primary and secondary flow, respectively. Figure 6 shows the gradient $\partial\bar{U}/\partial y$ field in the $x - z$ plane (Fig. 6a), together with the vorticity thickness of top and bottom shear layers for OP1-Exp, normalized by their respective primary nozzle exit vorticity thickness $\delta_{w,ne1}$ (Fig. 6b). An evaluation of the gradient $\partial\bar{U}/\partial y$ close to the wall reveals that the primary flow shear layer separates before the nozzle exit (see the left zoomed view in Fig. 6a). This separation is a direct result of the imposed discharge pressure at the outlet, as equally observed by Kracik and Dvorak [12] for the same configuration. In addition, the left zoomed view of Fig. 6a shows a recirculation zone of the secondary flow close to the wall in the nozzle exit region. This separation delays boundary layer growth, which only commences further downstream at roughly $x/d_{mc} = 3.7$. Thus, to enable an estimation of the vorticity thickness of the shear layer, the separation region of the secondary flow evident between $0 < x/d_{mc} < 3.7$ has been excluded from the calculation of δ_w . Between $0 < x/d_{mc} < 2$, vorticity thickness grows slowly, indicating a laminar shear layer. For $2 < x/d_{mc} < 3.5$, the growth of δ_w increases significantly, suggesting transition to turbulence, with a maximum at $x/d_{mc} = 3.5$. Further downstream, the transverse velocity gradient is much larger in the boundary layer than in the disappearing shear layer (for all $x/d_{mc} \geq 4$, as indicated in Fig. 6b). These findings agree qualitatively with results presented by Croquer et al. [11], although shear layer development happens on a much smaller axial extension in the present case due to the significantly reduced primary jet velocity.

Assuming constant specific heat capacities between primary and secondary flow, a convective Mach number $M_c = (\bar{u}_{ne1} - \bar{u}_{ne2})/(\bar{c}_{ne1} + \bar{c}_{ne2})$ is defined for the configuration. For the studied operating point OP1-Exp, $M_c = 0.29$, indicating that shear layer growth can be approximated by an incompressible approach [39]. With $K_u = \bar{u}_{ne2}/\bar{u}_{ne1}$ and $K_\rho = \bar{\rho}_{ne2}/\bar{\rho}_{ne1}$, the spatial vorticity thickness growth rate for an incompressible shear layer is given by an empirical correlation [40]:

$$\left(\frac{\partial\delta_w}{\partial x}\right)_{\rho=const.} = 0.165 \frac{(1 - K_u) \sqrt{1 + K_\rho}}{2\sqrt{1 + K_\rho K_u}} \quad (14)$$

For OP1-Exp, Eq. 14 predicts a theoretical vorticity thickness growth rate for an incompressible mixing layer of 0.0524. The actual vorticity thickness growth rate averaged between $0 \leq x/d_{mc} \leq 3.5$ and averaged between top and bottom shear is 0.0589, hence overestimating the ideal incompressible growth rate by roughly 12%. In light of the goals of this study, this result is deemed acceptable and confirms that shear layer development is sufficiently captured in the computation.

B. Analysis of Novel Operating Point Representative of RDC Exhaust

As shown in previous sections, a suitable computational setup for the ejector has been obtained. In order to study its behavior when subjected to pulsating flow, the operating point OP2-U (see Tab. 1) is implemented.

Fig. 6 (a) Time-averaged transverse velocity gradient $\partial\bar{U}/\partial y$ and (b) normalized vorticity thickness δ_w of bottom and top shear layers for OP1-Exp

1. General Flow Field Description

To describe the unsteady flow field, a single period of the pulsation is analyzed. The absolute time of the simulation is normalized by the convective time t_c , which refers to the time that a hypothetical weightless particle would require to be convected from the primary inlet to the outlet. For OP2-U, $t_c = 8.2 \times 10^{-3}$ s.

Figure 7 shows instantaneous static pressure fields for a single period ($t/t_c = 2.927$, Fig. 7a to $t/t_c = 3.018$, Fig. 7f), where the black line represents an isoline of Mach = 1. As expected, the nozzle exit velocity regime is periodically changing between subsonic and supersonic. At $t/t_c = 2.927$, the primary flow is choked but becomes subsonic shortly after the nozzle throat, whereas in the second half of the mixing chamber, a pressure wave is evident. Shortly after, at $t/t_c = 2.945$ (Fig. 7b), the flow unchokes completely in the primary nozzle, leading to an entirely subsonic domain. The pressure wave has moved upstream, following the reduction in primary inlet pressure. At $t/t_c = 2.963$ (Fig. 7c), a new pulse is introduced while the pressure wave has continued its upstream movement. After the interaction with the supersonic jet ($t/t_c = 2.981$, Fig. 7d), the pressure wave is located further downstream than in the previous snapshot. Soon after, a secondary shock forms at the mixing chamber exit ($t/t_c = 3.000$, Fig. 7e). With the pressure retracting, the shock strength diminishes ($t/t_c = 3.018$, Fig. 7f) and it eventually moves upstream as a pressure wave again, completing the periodic process.

The appearance of the secondary shock and the pressure wave observed in Fig. 7 requires further investigation. Thus, in the following, an attempt is made to track this movement visually using density gradient magnitude fields. Fig. 8 shows a time-space diagram of the secondary shock/pressure wave over a single period (the same period than shown in Fig. 7), complemented by five snapshots of the density gradient magnitude with an isoline of Mach = 1. The first time

Fig. 7 Instantaneous static pressure fields with a black isoline of Mach = 1 for six snapshots (a)-(f), corresponding to a single pulsation period for OP2-U

instant shown corresponds to $t/t_c = 2.927$ (i.e. to Fig. 7a), where the pressure wave is located at $x/d_{mc} \approx 10$ in an entirely subsonic mixing chamber. The pressure wave then moves upstream until it impinges the subsequent incoming supersonic jet at $t/t_c = 2.972$ and $x/d_{mc} = 3.3$ (bottom left). Subsequently, the pressure wave breaks up into two parts as the entering supersonic flow hinders any further upstream displacement in the primary flow section of the channel. One part convects downstream with the incoming pulse; this part has been tracked in Fig. 8. This pressure wave now starts dissipating into the flow, and the last instant where the pressure wave is still slightly visible is $t/t_c = 2.990$ at

$x/d_{mc} = 6.3$ (bottom right), although its surface is much more corrugated than before the interaction with the incoming jet. The other part of the pressure wave continues its upstream movement in the secondary, subsonic portion of the mixing chamber until it is evacuated at the secondary inlet boundary (not shown in Fig. 8). For $2.990 < t/t_c < 2.999$, there is no secondary shock nor pressure wave visually evident in the domain (dashed black line in the time-space plot). However, for $t/t_c > 2.999$, a shock eventually forms at $x/d_{mc} = 12$ (top right in Fig. 8) that has been observed previously. The shock remains at its position until $t/t_c = 3.027$. Upon this point, upstream pressure starts decreasing again and the periodic process repeats itself.

Fig. 8 Time-space diagram of the discontinuity observed for OP2-U, with zoomed views of the density gradient magnitude over an isoline of Mach = 1

In Fig. 9, the primary nozzle exit, secondary nozzle exit, and outlet mass fluxes are plotted over time. The resulting local entrainment ratio, denoted as ω , is illustrated on the right ordinate. The applied frequency of 1 kHz (refer to Table 1) is accurately captured for the primary flux, with discernible mass flux amplitudes of approximately $\pm 65\%$ from the mean value. The obtained mass flux fluctuations are larger than in a typical RDC exhaust (see e.g. Ref. [41]) as a result of the studied conventional circular ejector configuration with a relatively small nozzle exit cross-section compared to annular, existing RDCs. The pulsation of the primary flow introduces a perturbation in the entrainment of the secondary flow. In comparison to the primary flux, the pulsation amplitude of the secondary flow is relatively low. Consequently, the peaks in entrainment ratio primarily arise from the presence of small primary mass flow rates during fully unchoked, subsonic operation. The outlet mass flux pulsation frequency seems unchanged with respect to the primary nozzle exit, whereas the amplitude of the fluctuations is decreased significantly. A detailed analysis of fluctuation dampening throughout the device is presented in section III.B.4. The time-averaged entrainment ratio was $\bar{\omega} = 2.128$ in this case. Compared to classical ejector operating conditions, where $\omega < 1.2 - 1.3$ [9], this value is significantly elevated, which is coherent with experimental and numerical studies of RDC - ejector interaction [6, 15].

Fig. 9 Integrated primary (J_{ne1}) and secondary (J_{ne2}) mass fluxes at the nozzle exit, outlet mass flux (J_4) and local entrainment ratio $\omega = \dot{m}_{ne2}/\dot{m}_{ne1}$

2. Instantaneous Velocity Profiles

Figure 10 shows instantaneous axial velocity profiles for five different axial stations between $0 \leq x/d_{mc} \leq 12$ (Figs. 10a to 10e). The profiles are normalized by the time-averaged primary nozzle exit velocity \bar{u}_{ne1} . At $x/d_{mc} = 0$, the maximum fluctuation amplitude of roughly 150% occurs between $t/t_c = 2.957$ and $t/t_c = 2.988$, which is coherent with previous observations at this time instant. The velocity profile for $t/t_c = 2.988$ changes its shape from a single maximum on the jet centerline (bell-shape) to two symmetrical maxima located on the boundary between primary jet and secondary flow between $x/d_{mc} = 0$ and $x/d_{mc} = 1$ (Figs. 10a and 10b), a result indicating that the ejector behaves as a classical ejector at this time instant [11]. Further downstream at $x/d_{mc} = 3$ (Fig. 10c), this profile characteristic is not observed due to mixing between both flows. While the axial velocity for $t/t_c = 2.988$ reduces significantly throughout the mixing chamber from a maximum of $u/\bar{u}_{ne1} = 2$ (Fig. 10a) to $u/\bar{u}_{ne1} \approx 0.7$ (Fig. 10e), at time instant of $t/t_c = 2.957$, the axial velocity changes only between $0.8 \leq u/\bar{u}_{ne1} \leq 1.0$ along the mixing chamber. At both other time instants, $t/t_c = 3.018$ and $t/t_c = 2.927$, axial velocity changes throughout the domain are within the limits of both other time instants evaluated. At $x/d_{mc} = 12$, the influence of the secondary shock is evident for $t/t_c = 3.018$ (Fig. 10e). Interestingly, the velocity profiles seem to align relatively well over time at $x/d_{mc} = 8$ (Fig. 10d). The result suggests that the ejector is capable of dampening the primary flow fluctuations to a certain extent, and doing so on an axial distance shorter than the total ejector length of the investigated configuration, both of which are considered generally favorable for gas turbine integration.

Fig. 10 (a)-(e) Instantaneous velocity profiles between axial planes $x/d_{mc} = 0$ and $x/d_{mc} = 12$ during a single fluctuation period for OP2-U

3. Kinetic Energy Dissipation

Second law analysis is an appropriate tool to assess losses in available work through turbomachinery components [42]. A detailed loss analysis and as a consequence, a minimization of these losses is a crucial step in ensuring adequate performance of an RDC-ejector configuration, as mentioned in section I. Without mass transfer and chemical reactions in the system, and neglecting any coupling effects, the irreversible entropy generation rate reads [43]:

$$\dot{S}_{gen} = \frac{\lambda}{T^2} \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial x_i} \right)^2 + \frac{\tau_{ij}}{T} \frac{\partial U_i}{\partial x_j} \quad (15)$$

The kinetic energy and heat transfer loss terms Π_{KE} and Π_{TE} can be derived by a multiplication of both sides in Eq. 15 with the temperature. In a LES context, the subgrid-scale contributions need to be considered, which leads to the following form for both loss terms [42]:

$$\Pi_{TE} = \overline{\frac{\lambda + \lambda^{SGS}}{\bar{T}} \left(\frac{\partial \tilde{T}}{\partial x_i} \right)^2} \quad (16)$$

$$\Pi_{KE} = \overline{\frac{1}{2} (\mu + \mu^{SGS}) \left(\frac{\partial \tilde{U}_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial \tilde{U}_j}{\partial x_i} - \frac{2}{3} \frac{\partial \tilde{U}_i}{\partial x_j} \delta_{ij} \right) \left(\frac{\partial \tilde{U}_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial \tilde{U}_j}{\partial x_i} \right)} \quad (17)$$

As pointed out by Inhestern et al. [44], heat transfer losses in adiabatic flow are irrelevant for the shaft power generation in the turbine. In addition, a volume-integration of both terms revealed that Π_{TE} is an order of magnitude lower than Π_{KE} , which is coherent with literature [45]. As a consequence, Π_{TE} is not further considered in the remainder of the work.

In Fig. 11, a two-dimensional map of Π_{KE} and respective profiles along the ejector mixing chamber and diffuser are shown for OP2-U, where time-averaging of Π_{KE} was performed over 25 periods. As evident from Fig. 11a, for $x/d_{mc} < 12$, losses concentrate in the boundary layer and in the shear layer, which is clearly visible as a loss source

downstream of the nozzle exit. The secondary shock, located at $x/d_{mc} = 12$, introduces additional losses. In an attempt to quantify the relative loss contribution of the secondary shock, the region around $x/d_{mc} = 12$ where the shock is located in the time-averaged solution, was isolated from the rest of the domain. Subsequently, Π_{KE} was volume-integrated in the isolated region and in the entire ejector (excluding the primary inlet channel up towards $x/d_{mc} = 0$). Results showed that the secondary shock has only a minor influence on $\int \Pi_{KE} dV$, with a value of roughly 3%. Further downstream, flow separation in the diffuser increases Π_{KE} at the wall and in the jet centerline in the region $12 < x/d_{mc} < 19$. Figures 11b to 11i show 8 axial cuts of the kinetic energy loss along the mixing chamber and diffuser. The development of the shear layer and the concentration of losses within it is clearly evident. For both $1 < x/d_{mc} < 3$ (Figs. 11b to 11d), losses in the shear layer are at least as high as in the boundary layer. Outside of the shear layer and the boundary layer, losses are minimal at these axial positions. At $x/d_{mc} = 6$ (Fig. 11f), the shear layer has disappeared (as also visible in Fig. 11a) and Π_{KE} is roughly constant in the central region of the channel. The lowest centerline value of Π_{KE} is obtained at $x/d_{mc} = 12$ (Fig. 11h). As derived previously, flow separation in the diffuser then leads to another increase in losses at $x/d_{mc} = 16$ (Fig. 11i).

4. Unsteadiness Analysis

An important objective of an ejector placed between RDC and turbine is the dampening of RDC exhaust gas fluctuations, which are considered detrimental for turbine operation [7]. The parameter $D = (\Phi_{max} - \Phi_{min})/\Phi_{mean}$, evaluated over a single period of the fluctuation, where Φ is an arbitrary, time-dependent quantity and the indices *max*, *min* and *mean* refer to time, allows the calculation of the dampening factor [7]:

$$\xi = \frac{D_{ne1} - D_3}{D_{ne1}} \quad (18)$$

The factor is applied between the nozzle exit at axial plane *ne1* and plane 3, which refers to the exit of the diffusing section (see Fig. 1), instead of the ejector outlet at station 4 to remove any possible dampening effects related to decreasing mesh resolution. To obtain a single value in the non-uniform axial planes *ne1* and 3, the total pressure field has been massflow-averaged and the static pressure field area-averaged, which are appropriate averaging techniques [46]. The dampening factor ξ was then calculated for 15 single periods for both static and total pressure signals and results were subsequently averaged. The metric revealed that the amplitude of total pressure fluctuations is reduced by about 85%, whereas the static pressure fluctuation amplitude is reduced by about 70% between primary nozzle exit and diffuser exit. This result is consistent with experimental measurements in an RDC - ejector configuration [6]. Figure 12 shows the time-dependent evolution of mass-flow averaged total pressure (Fig. 12a), a Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) of the same quantity (Fig. 12b) and the time-dependent evolution of area-averaged static pressure (Fig. 12c) at the primary nozzle exit plane (total pressure $P_{t,ne1}^m$, static pressure $P_{s,ne1}^A$) and diffuser exit plane (total pressure P_{t3}^m , static

(a)

Fig. 11 (a) Time-averaged 2D field of the Loss in Kinetic Energy (Π_{KE}), and (b)-(i) transverse fields of Π_{KE} above a line trace along $y/d_{mc} = 0$ for OP2-U

pressure P_{s3}^A). The quantities have been normalized by their respective time-averaged values. Figures 12a and 12c corroborate the results mentioned above for the dampening of total and static pressure fluctuations. The periodically appearing second peak in static pressure at the nozzle exit (visible e.g. at $t/t_c \approx 2.2$, $t/t_c \approx 2.235$ in Fig. 12c) is a result of the unsteady shock diamond structure moving periodically through the nozzle exit (as also seen in Fig. 7). The total

pressure pulsation at the nozzle exit is distributed over three harmonics, with a clear peak at the imposed frequency of 1 kHz. Throughout the mixing chamber and diffuser, the frequency spectrum is retained, as indicated by the peaks of the blue trace in Fig. 12b. The diffuser outlet pressure fluctuation amplitudes are considered much more favorable for turbine integration than the nozzle exit signal [47].

Fig. 12 Evaluation of (a)-(b) total pressure and (c) static pressure unsteadiness between primary flow nozzle exit and diffuser exit

IV. Conclusions

A numerical study on the effect of axially pulsating inflow on a conventional ejector configuration has been conducted, with the intent of installing such a device downstream of an RDC chamber. In the first stage of the study, a stationary operating point (OP1-Exp) was computed which showed good agreement with available experimental data. The vorticity thickness growth rate of the shear layer in this case was within 12% of an empirical reference value. Subsequently, a completely new operating condition (OP2-U) was selected, where a sinusoidal acoustic pulsation was imposed at the primary inlet boundary. The pulsation was chosen in a way that the primary nozzle throat periodically chokes and unchokes, generating a flow fluctuating between subsonic and supersonic velocity regimes at the nozzle exit, which is representative of an RDC exhaust. The effects of mean temperature, gas composition and flow angle fluctuations were ignored.

An analysis of kinetic energy dissipation revealed that the boundary layer, the shear layer between primary and secondary flow and the flow separation induced in the diffuser are among the main loss sources. Additionally, it was found that the unsteady operating condition leads to the periodic presence of a discontinuity, although it had only a minor impact on the volume-integrated kinetic energy dissipation. The presence of this discontinuity demonstrated that an unsteady approach is necessary to characterize RDC - ejector interaction. On the other hand, the ejector was capable

of reducing approximately 70% of the static and 85% of the total pressure fluctuation amplitude, whereas total pressure fluctuation frequency was equal between diffuser outlet and nozzle exit. Instantaneous velocity profiles showed that axial velocities align relatively well at an axial distance of $x/d_{mc} = 8$, which is about a third of the total ejector length downstream of the nozzle exit. These findings are considered favorable for RDC integration and showcase the potential of utilizing an ejector as an intermediate component between RDC and axial turbine. Future work should include the implementation of temperature effects, flow angle fluctuations and gas composition in the RDC exhaust gas. Moreover, with a dedicated design study more adapted to pulsating flows, some of the previously mentioned loss sources and internal phenomena could probably be mitigated while retaining the dampening characteristics.

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